

THE ISSUE OF ADEQUACY IN LITERARY TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

Despite the centuries-old history of the translation process and the ongoing study of its various aspects, many problems have not yet received a clear and definitive solution. The problem of assessing the quality of translation falls into this category. The question of how exactly it is necessary to translate in order to bring the translation into line with the original has become relevant with the advent of written translations and has not yet found its solution. This article discusses the concept of adequacy, as well as the tasks and issues of applying this concept in literary translation. In addition, the article discusses the use of units associated with the process of translating works of art from one language to another using the method of adequate translation.

Introduction. An adequate translation is a translation that pragmatically ensures the maximum equivalence of the tasks of the translation act to achieve this goal, without violating the norms of the use of words and their forms established in the language. For an adequate translation of information transmitted only by language symbols, for example, a clearly expressed meaning in the text will not be enough. Some linguists distinguish between what they call an adequate translation, a translation based only on the meanings expressed by linguistic signs, and an interpretation that includes extralinguistic information. According to V. S. Vinogradov, equivalence in translation theory should be understood as “the preservation of the relative equality

of content, semantic, stylistic and functional-communicative information in the original and in the translation. At the same time, the equivalence of the original and the translation affects, first of all, the general understanding of the information contained in the text, including not only the mind, but also the emotions of the recipient. only pronounced. in the text, but also indirectly mentioned in the subtext. Equivalence - semantic, semantic, stylistic and functional - ensuring the relative equality of communicative information. A translation that is necessary and sufficient to convey an unchanged content plan is an equivalent translation that complies with FL standards. This definition was given by Yu.I.S. Barkhudarov, definitions by V.S.

Vinogradov and L.S. equivalence of translation, among which the following general requirements can be distinguished: respect for equality in the transfer of different types of information, that is, a meaningful plan. In addition, translation requires a certain amount of technical and scientific knowledge. A successful translator should always be a bit of an ethnographer, historian, politician. Vinogradov believes that the equivalence of a translation to the original is always a relative concept. It can be argued that any translation will never be identical to the canonical text of the original. The degree of similarity with the original depends on many factors - the skill of the translator, the features of comparing languages and cultures, the method of translation, the nature of the translated texts.

Some ways to achieve adequacy:

When redistributing the content, the meaning of one word can be divided into several words and vice versa. Perhaps this is a change in the categorical affiliation of words, for example, a verb is used instead of a noun, an adverb is used instead of an adjective.

The syntactic structure of the sentence also changes, which can be expressed in a complete restructuring. This method includes cases when the value of the entire part of the source text is not transferred to the value of individual elements of the source text. In this case, apparently, you should proceed as follows:

- - understanding the meaning of the original statement;
- - ignoring the specific way of expressing this value;

In many cases, it is necessary to use translation changes, since there are often

scientific and technical texts, parts and even individual sentences of which cannot be translated verbatim or are not specific to other languages due to or due to construction features. the presence of phrases, expressions or terms that are not interchangeable in the text.

All kinds of changes introduced during the translation process can be reduced to four elementary types, namely:

Alterations are changes in the arrangement of language elements in the translated text relative to the source text. The elements that can be rearranged are usually words, phrases, parts of a complex sentence and independent sentences in the text.

Substitutions are the most common and varied type of translation transformation. In the process of translation, both grammatical and lexical units can be replaced, so we can talk about grammatical and lexical substitutions. The grammatical types include the following types: exchange of word forms, exchange of sentence fragments, exchange of sentence members (reconstruction of the syntactic structure of a sentence), syntactic exchanges in a complex sentence;

Conclusion. The adequacy of the translation should be understood. Adequacy means that the translation as a process corresponds to these communicative conditions. These methods help to achieve the adequacy of the translation. But the translator must translate from his native language into a foreign one, or vice versa, from a foreign language into his native language, only then he will achieve complete identity and adequacy.

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